

**THE EFFECT OF QUALITY OF WORK-LIFE ON THE JOB
SATISFACTION, WORK MOTIVATION, AND WORK
PERFORMANCE OF HOTEL EMPLOYEES IN WEST LOMBOK**

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Abstract

Quality of work-life is one of the factors that affect employee performance. Every employee working in a hotel must have standards that help identify with the quality of work-life standards. This study aimed to examine the effect of quality of work-life on job satisfaction, work motivation, and performance of the tourism workforce at hotels in West Lombok. The model used in this research is influence and relationship. The analytical tool used in processing the data to test the proposed hypothesis uses SEM, which is operated through the AMOS and SPSS programs. Based on the analysis results, it is known that the dominant employee performance is influenced by work motivation variables and job satisfaction variables. Based on the total direct effect calculation, the variable that gives the strongest total influence is the variable quality of work-life on the motivation of 0.245. The result shows that the quality of work-life has a strong impact on work motivation, and improving employee performance can be done by increasing employee motivation.

Keywords: Influence, Quality of work-life, employee, hotel

1. Introduction

One of the efforts to manage the workforce so that they can work comfortably and increase work productivity and meet the needs of employees is by implementing quality of work-life (Siagian, 2004). Quality of work-life is one of the factors that affect employee performance. The minimum quality of work-life is fulfilled by implementing the Manpower Act no. 13 of 2003, which regulates equal opportunity and treatment, job training, employment relations, protection, wages, employee welfare, and industrial relations. It is very important that every employee who works in a hotel must have standards that help identify with the standard of quality of work-life (Kandasamy & Sreekumar, 2009).

High quality of work-life is achieved if the employee gets job satisfaction both in participating in decision making and has the opportunity to develop. The quality of their working life also influences the motivation of employees to work as workers. Employees who are not motivated will certainly not be able to provide full service to tourists. High motivation will create responsibility in every work done (Pratiwi & Himam, 2014). In addition, the quality of work-life is very important to be appropriately implemented by the company for the company's long-term sustainability in retaining its best employees to keep working with high motivation and performance. Companies that have and implement a good quality of work-life represent that they have good supervision, good working conditions; good salary and benefits; and attractive rewards and challenging work (Werther & Davis, 2006).

Employees who have high work motivation and job satisfaction will affect customer satisfaction. Job satisfaction is part of life satisfaction; if individuals have satisfaction in their work, their performance tends to increase (Gibson, 2012). Luthans (2006) defines job satisfaction as a happy emotional state or positive emotion from job appraisal or work experience. Satisfied employees are motivated employees; they have the motivational resources to provide good services. In addition, these employees will have high energy and willingness to provide good service, so it is said that the empowerment of human resources has the strongest influence to support organizational performance improvement (Sutawa, 2015).

The tourism area in West Lombok was chosen as the research location because of the large number of hotels and workers compared to other districts in NTB. In addition, West Lombok Regency is the center of the first tourism development area and the most visited by tourists. Local people who work in tourism areas, especially in West

Lombok, must be able to deal with the situation and hotel management both locally, nationally, and internationally with all binding work regulations. This quality of work-life must be carried out by hotels and employees so that all aspects of life can run well in the tourism area in Lombok, considering Lombok as an area that has a diversity of ethnicities and religions as well as a diverse cultural life.

Based on the background, this research aims to find out the effect of the quality of work-life on job satisfaction, work motivation, and work performance of tourism workers at hotels in West Lombok?

2. Literature Review

Theory Quality of Work-life

Quality of work-life was first introduced at the international labor relations conference in 1972 at Arden House, Columbia University, New York. Quality of work-life became a concern after the *United Auto Workers and General Motors* started a quality of the work-life program for work change. The quality of the work-life program was initially focused on the needs of female workers and later extended to all employees. The development of the quality of work-life is intended to help balance work with the needs, interests, and pressures faced by employees to increase company productivity and reduce employee turnover (Koonmee et al., 2010).

May et al. (1999) suggested that quality of work-life is favorable conditions and environment in the workplace that supports and enhances employee satisfaction by providing them with rewards, job security, and growth opportunities. The opinion of May et al. (1999) implies that the quality of work-life is a process in which an organization reacts to the needs of employees through the development of decision-making mechanisms that allow employees to fully participate in designing their lives at work and are beneficial for increasing organizational productivity.

Cummings & Worley (2014), Bernardin, HJ and Russell (1993) stated that the quality of work-life is related to individual experiences in obtaining satisfaction, increased motivation, work involvement, and commitment to work-life, where individuals get satisfaction in fulfilling personal needs, such as the need for freedom when working in organizations. Cascio (2010) and Luthan (2006) describe the quality of work-life as employees' perceptions of their mental and physical well-being when working where employees feel safe, satisfied, and have the opportunity to grow and develop as human beings. Respect for humans in their work environment is an effort to

make the work environment better and lead to a better quality of work-life and bring benefits to the company.

According to Walton (1973) in Horst et al. (2014), there are eight indicators in the quality of work-life as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1.
The Practices of Quality of Work-life (Walton, 1973)

Satisfaction Theory

This theory was first put forward by Herzberg (1996) through research results by dividing situations that affect a person's attitude towards his work into two groups, namely: satisfiers group, situations that are proven to be a source of job satisfaction. The presence of this factor will lead to satisfaction, but its absence does not always result in dissatisfaction. The dissatisfiers group are the factors that have been proven to be a source of dissatisfaction. Improvements to this condition will reduce or eliminate dissatisfaction but will not lead to satisfaction because it is not a source of job satisfaction.

In this study, the measurement of job satisfaction utilizes the concept of job satisfaction from Smith (in SP Robbins & Judge, 2015) that five dimensions affect job satisfaction, namely:

1. The work itself, the extent to which the job provides an opportunity for a person to learn to take responsibility in a particular task and challenge for an interesting job.
2. Payment, the wages earned by a person in proportion to the effort made and the same as the wages received by others in the same work position.
3. Opportunity for promotion, the opportunity for someone to reach or be promoted to a higher level in the organization.

4. Superiors, the ability of superiors to provide technical assistance and support for the work that is the responsibility of subordinates.
5. Co-workers, proficient and socially supportive of other co-workers' duties.

Motivation Theory

Maslow & Frager (2007) divided human needs into five hierarchies of needs, namely:

1. Physiological Needs

These needs involve basic human needs, namely clothing, food, housing, and individual welfare. This need is very primary because this need has existed and has been felt since humans were born.

2. Needs of Security

Security needs not only physical safety but also psychological security and fair treatment in employment. Safety in the physical sense includes the security of a person in the area of residence, on the way to work, and security at work.

3. Social Needs

Social needs are reflected in 4 (four) forms of feelings, namely the need to feel accepted by others with whom he associates and interacts in the organization, and thus he has a high sense of belonging. It must be accepted as the fact that everyone has a unique identity with all its advantages and disadvantages. With this identity, every human being feels that he is essential, meaning he has a sense of importance. The need for a sense of progress and not to fail is often called a sense of accomplishment. No one is happy when he meets failure, and on the contrary, he is happy when he meets success.

4. Self-Esteem Need

The higher a person's position, the more things are used as a symbol of his status. In organizational life, there are many facilities that a person and organization obtain to show their status in the organization. Experience shows that both in traditional societies and advanced societies.

5. Self-Actualization

This need is based on the capabilities that need to be developed to contribute to the interests of the organization. Through increasing workability, they will be able to satisfy their various needs, and at this level, people tend to develop themselves and do better continuously.

Performance

Nawawi (2016) stated that performance is achieved, the achievements are shown, and workability. Work performance is said to be high if a work target can be completed at the right time or does not exceed the time limit provided. Performance is said to be low if it is completed beyond the allotted time limit or is not completed. In line with Hasibuan (2005), which also states that performance results from work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience, sincerity, and time and performance are a combination of three important factors, namely the ability and interest of a worker, the ability and acceptance of the explanation of the delegation of tasks and roles as well as the level of motivation of workers.

Robbins & Judge (2007) also explain indicators to measure employee performance individually; there are five indicators, namely:

1. Quality is measured from employee perceptions of the quality of the work produced and the perfection of tasks on the skills and abilities of employees.
2. Quantity is the amount produced expressed in terms such as the number of units, the number of activity cycles completed.
3. Timeliness is the level of activity completed at the beginning of the stated time, seen and from the point of coordination with the results *output* and maximizing the time available for other activities.
4. Effectiveness is the extent to which the use of organizational resources (human resources, money, technology, raw materials) is maximized to increase results and each unit in the use of resources.
5. Independence is the level of an employee who will carry out his work functions independently and demonstrate work commitment and work responsibilities towards his company.

3. Research Methods

This research aims to measure the effect of the quality of work-life on work performance in West Lombok hotel employees by examining the influence of quality of work-life on employee performance.

Sample and Research Location

The location of this research is in West Lombok, NTB Province. In particular, this research was conducted at hotels in West Lombok. There are 16 hotels in West Lombok district, which are used as research samples.

The size of the sample in a study has a vital role in the interpretation of SEM results. The number of sample sizes will provide a basis for estimating the sampling error. With the estimation model using Maximum Likelihood (ML), a minimum sample of 100 is required. When the sample is increased above the value of 100, the ML method increases its sensitivity to detect differences between data. Once the sample becomes large, the ML method becomes very sensitive and will produce significant differences so that the Goodness-of-fit measure is not good. So it can be recommended that a sample size between 100 to 200 be used for the ML estimation method (Ghozali, 2014). So the sample in this study was 250 samples.

Types of Data

The data used are qualitative data and quantitative data. This study uses qualitative data, namely data in the form of explanations, descriptions of certain phenomena related to research on workers' quality of working life at hotels in West Lombok. Qualitative data include literature, and in the form of responses as well as qualitative data that is the object of analysis, the results of in-depth interviews with workers, statements from previous researchers are used to support research results. The quantitative data, namely data in the form of numbers to support qualitative data. The quantitative data included in this study are the number of accommodations, the number of workers, the data from the questionnaire table, and the results of the SEM analysis.

Data Collection Methods The data

collection techniques used in this study are:

1. Questionnaires are a number of written questions used to obtain information from respondents in terms of reports about their personalities or things they know (Sangadji, 2010).
2. The interview in this study is a supporting method of the main method in the form of a questionnaire. Interviews will be conducted with workers who work at hotels that are the object of research and as research samples based on the questionnaire that has been prepared.
3. A literature study is studying various reference books and similar previous research results to obtain information about the problem to be checked (Sarwono, 2006).

This study will use textbooks and papers related to the problem under study.

Data Analysis

The model used in this study is influence and relationship. The analytical tool used in processing the data to test the proposed hypothesis uses SEM, which is operated

through the AMOS and SPSS version 22 programs. This study uses two kinds of analytical techniques, namely

1. Confirmatory factor analysis is used to confirm the factors involved
2. Regression Weight in SEM is used to examine how much the variables of quality of work-life, job satisfaction, work motivation, self-efficacy, and employee performance influence each other.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Respondents' assessment of the Quality of Work-life variable can be seen in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4. 1
Respondent's Assessment on the Quality of Work-life Variable

	Indicator	Total Score	Average	Std deviation
X1	Fair salary system.	1067	4.27	0.624
X2	Work environment, work equipment, working hours, working conditions that minimize the risk of accidents.	1022	4.09	0.797
X3	Opportunity to attend training or continue education.	1063	4.25	0.631
X4	Opportunity to advance in the future career.	984	3.94	0.674
X5	Opportunity to interact with colleagues	1024	4.10	0.775
X6	Freedom to express idea and opinion	979	3.92	0.704
X7	The balance between work time, time with family, vacation time, social time	1029	4.12	0.765
X8	The existence of CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) activities	956	3.82	0.761
			4.064	0.716

(Source: Data Research, 2020)

Respondents' assessment of the variable Quality of Work-life of hotels workers in West Lombok is an average of 4,064 with a standard deviation of 0.716, which can be categorized as good. This showed that the average respondent gives an Agree assessment on this Quality of Work-life variable. Respondents gave the highest rating on the indicator of a fair remuneration system in accordance with the position of 4.27. This indicates that the employee's wages or salaries are in accordance with the position as an effort to increase motivation and productivity in doing work. The lowest indicator is CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) activities with an average score of 3.82, which indicates that the hotel's commitment as a form

of responsibility to the environment and society is aimed at empowering the community and, in a sense, responsibility of care for the environment. This can be seen from the lack of activities in helping the poor, and the education of the surrounding community is still not getting enough attention.

Table 4. 2
Respondents' Assessment on Job Satisfaction Variables

	Indicator	Total score	Average	Std deviation
Y1.1	Challenges and job responsibilities given	991	3.96	0.773
Y1.2	Wages received.	920	3.68	0.516
Y1.3	Promotion of positions given	911	3.64	0.715
Y1.4	The supervisor who is always willing to provide technical assistance and support to the work of subordinates	942	3.77	0.672
Y1.5	Support from colleagues in carrying out work	958	3.83	0.824
			3.78	0.70

(Source: Data Research, 2020)

Table 4.2 showed that the average respondent's assessment of job satisfaction at five-star hotels in West Lombok is satisfied with a score of 3.78 with a standard deviation of 0.70, which can be categorized as good. The highest satisfaction is at a score of 3.96, namely the indicator of being satisfied with the challenges and responsibilities of the work given. The indicator satisfied with the promotion offered has the lowest level of satisfaction (3.64) because the promotion is still not felt by employees.

Table 4. 3
Respondents' Assessment on Work Motivation

	Indicators	Total Score	Average	Std deviation
Y2.1	availability of workspace complete with adequate safety devices that can motivate more comfortable working with	991	3.86	0655
Y2.2	Salary provided can motivate to work	920	3.78	0.738
Y2.3	Benefits motivate at work	911	3.82	0.714
Y2.4	A harmonious relationship between leaders and subordinates can motivate work	942	3.94	0.680

Y2.5	Rewards for work performance provide motivation at work	958	3.52	0.616
			3.78	0.680

(Source: Data Research, 2020)

Table 4.3 states that the respondents' assessment of work motivation with an average score of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 0.680 is in a good category. This shows that the average respondent agrees with work motivation at hotels in West Lombok. On the indicator that a harmonious relationship between leaders and subordinates can motivate workers, the respondents gave the highest score of 3.94. While the indicators of work performance awards provide motivation to work, the lowest score of 3.52 indicates that the employees in West Lombok hotels have not received enough appreciation for their hard work and achievements.

Table 4. 4
Variable Rate Respondents Against Employee Performance

	Indicators	Total score	Average	Std deviation
Y3.1	ability complete the work in accordance with the standards and procedures	993	3.97	0610
Y3.2	ability to finish some work on target	1015	4:06	0.700
Y3.3	The ability to complete basic tasks and other tasks on time	1034	4.14	0.769
Y3.4	The ability to use existing resources to the fullest to help increase the level of work production.	1021	4.08	0.829
Y3.5	Be responsible for any work given by superiors	1012	4.05	0.675
Y3.6	Ability to comply with work discipline in accordance with hotel regulations	1077	4.31	0.709
			4.10	0.72

(Source: Data Research, 2020)

The average score on respondents' assessment of the performance variable shows an average value of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.72 in the good category. This shows that the performance of employees at five-star hotels in West Lombok is high. Performance with indicators of ability to comply with work discipline in accordance with hotel regulations shows the highest score of 4.31. This shows that the workforce has complied with work discipline in accordance with the regulations set by the hotel. The score that shows the lowest performance lies in the indicator of the ability

to complete work in accordance with standards and procedures, with a score of 3.97. This indicates that the ability of hotel employees in West Lombok to complete work in accordance with standards and procedures still needs to be improved.

The degree of accuracy achieved by the indicators measured makes it necessary to test each variable's construct validity. Requirements are *Unidimensional* required for reliability analysis and construct validation (Anderson and Gerbing, 1998). The indicator of each variable is declared valid if the *loading factor* of each indicator is significant. Ferdinand (2002) states that the *loading factor* (standard coefficient) or lambda value can be said to be significant if it has a value of 0.40 and the value of $p = 0.000$ is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$ in the *regression weight*. The test results show that the magnitude of the loading factor on all indicators is above 0.5. Overall the results of the calculation of *construct reliability* and *variance construct* can be seen in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5
Construct Reliability and Variance Construct

Variable / construct	Variance Extract (VE)	Construct Reliability (CR)
X1 (Quality of Work-life)	0818	0973
Y1 (Job Satisfaction)	0639	0890
Y2 (Work Motivation)	0670	0909
Y3 (Performance)	0811	0962

The table above indicates that the value of *construct reliability* (CR) is greater than 0.5, and the *variance extract* (VE) is greater than 0.7. The results of the calculation of VE and CR indicate that the research model is acceptable.

Results of Confirmatory Analysis

Research Variables Confirmatory analysis is used to ensure the validity of each indicator that forms the construct and confirms all indicators that make up each variable. Confirmatory factor analysis is also intended to analyze the level of validity of the data in this study. This means that the indicators used have sufficient meaning to define the latent variables that are formed. According to Ferdinand (2006), a significant indicator defines the latent variable if it has lambda (λ) 0.5 and critical value (CR) 2.00 and probability < 0.05 . If the loading factor or standard coefficient is 0.4, the presence of an indicator is stated to be strong enough to measure a construct.

Based on the research model from the structural equation model, confirmatory factor analysis was carried out using the Amos for windows version 22 program. Table 4.6 shows that the confirmatory factor analysis showed significant results. This is evidenced by the CR value greater than 1.96 or p-value less than 0.05, and the standard coefficient value or loading factor is more than 0.4. The results of the confirmatory analysis of research variables can be seen in table below:

Table 4.6
Results of Confirmatory Analysis of Research Variables

	Indicator	Standard Coefficient	SE	CR	p-Value
X1	Fair salary system.	0.985	.038	26,709	***
X2	Work environment, work equipment, working hours, working conditions that minimize the risk of accidents.	0.835	.017	58.917	***
X3	Opportunity to attend training or continue education.	0.993	.038	27,557	***
X4	Opportunity to advance in the future career.	0.761	.050	17.181	***
X5	Opportunity to interact with colleagues	0.825	.060	17.749	***
X6	Freedom of expression	0.760	.058	15.114	***
X7	The balance between work time, time with family, vacation time, social time	0.826	.016	61.903	***
X8	The existence of CSR (<i>Corporate Social Responsibility</i>) activities	0.738	.058	14,618	***
Y1.1	Challenges and job responsibilities given	0.935	.364	6.148	***
Y1.2	Wages received.	.727	.196	5934	***
Y1.3	Romosi given positions	.780	.285	6046	***
Y1.4	Bosses were always willing to provide technical assistance and support for the work of subordinates	.446	.214	4348	***
Y1.5	Support colleagues in perform work	.392	.073	6148	***
Y2.1	Availability of workspace complete with adequate safety devices that can motivate more comfortable working with	0,765	.138	8705	***
Y2.2	salary given to provide motivation to work	.692	.116	8771	***
Y2.3	allowances to motivate the work	.557	.093	8.545	***
Y2.4	the harmonious relationship between leaders and subordinates can be motivated to work	.771	.115	9070	***
Y2.5	Achievement Awards in job motivating work	.680	.096	8.705	***
Y3.1	Ability to complete work in accordance with standards and procedures	0.691	.058	12,217	***
Y3.2	The ability to use existing resources to the fullest to help increase the level of work production.	0.851	.061	16,363	***

Y3.3	Be responsible for any work given by superiors	0,849	.064	17 070	***
Y3.4	Ability to comply with work discipline in accordance with hotel regulations	.874	.069	17 474	***
Y3.5	Responsible in every job supervisor	.816	.059	15 726	***
Y3.6	Capabilities comply with labor discipline in accordance with regulationshotels	0,844	.116	12 217	***

In accordance with the theory and the results of testing the previous hypothesis, the quality of work-life has a direct or indirect influence on employee performance. The indirect effect is by first passing through job satisfaction and work motivation which in turn affects employee performance. The results of testing the direct and indirect effects can be seen in table 4.7 as follows:

Table 4.7
Direct Effects Between the Variables of Quality of Work-life, Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation, and Performance of Hotel Workers in West Lombok

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Direct Effect (direct effect)	Effect Indirect (Indirect effects)	Effects of Total (Total Effect)
Quality of work-life	→ performance	0196	0000	0196
Quality of work-life	→ work Motivation	0219	0000	0219
Quality of work-life	→ Job satisfaction	0217	0000	0217
Quality of work-life	→ job satisfaction → performance	0196	0047	0243
Quality Work-life	→Motivation → Performance	0.196	0.049	0.245

From the results of the analysis in the table above, the magnitude of the direct effect, indirect effect, and total effect can be explained as follows:

- a) The *direct effect* of the variable quality of work-life on job satisfaction has a value of 0.217; the *indirect effect* value is 0.000 so that the *total effect value* is 0.217.
- b) The *direct effect* of the variable quality of work-life on work motivation has a value of 0.219; the value of the *indirect effect* is 0.000, so that the value of the total effect is 0.219.
- c) The *direct effect* of the quality of work-life on performance has a value of 0.196, the value of the *indirect effect* is 0.000 so that the value of the *total effect* is 0.196.

- d) The *direct effect* on the quality of work-life on performance has a value of 0.196; the value of the *indirect effect* through job satisfaction is 0.047, so that the value of the total effect is 0.243.
- e) The direct effect on the quality of work-life on performance has a value of 0.196, the value of the indirect effect through work motivation is 0.049 so that the value of the total effect (total effect) is 0.245.

Based on the analysis above, the value of the standardized direct effect, the largest direct effect occurs on the variable quality of work-life on the work motivation of 0.219 and the influence of quality of work-life on job satisfaction of 0.217. From the value of the standardized indirect effect, it can be seen that the indirect effect on the quality of work-life on employee performance is 2.45 through the work motivation variable and 0.243 through the job satisfaction variable.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study indicate that employee performance is predominantly influenced by work motivation and job satisfaction variables compared to self-efficacy and work ethic variables. Based on the calculation of the total direct effect, the variable that gives the strongest total influence is the variable quality of work-life on motivation of 0.245. This shows that the quality of work-life has a strong influence on work motivation, and improving employee performance can be done by increasing employee motivation.

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